

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Gulomjonov Odiljon Rahimjon ugli

REGULATION OF FAMILY RELATIONS INVOLVING FOREIGN
CITIZENS AND STATELESS PERSONS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/IYUN

HONORED
MENTION

YOUR
SEAL